

ASSESSING THE DETERMINANTS AND IMPACTS OF VEHICULAR TRAFFIC CONGESTION IN URBAN CORRIDORS AND PUBLIC HEALTH IN ENUGU STATE

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ABSTRACT

Urban traffic congestion is one of the most pressing challenges facing medium-sized African cities, impeding mobility, productivity, and public health. This study assesses the causes, impacts, and mitigation strategies of vehicular traffic congestion in Enugu, Nigeria. A structured questionnaire was administered to 400 commuters, with 360 valid responses analyzed using descriptive statistics. Results show that inadequate road capacity (79.4%), poor driver behavior (76.7%), and insufficient bus stop design (76.4%) are major contributors. Over 63% of respondents reported daily delays exceeding 45 minutes. A notable 43% estimated that traffic-related fatalities ranged between 50–100 annually, highlighting perceived public health risks. While based on subjective perceptions, the study underscores the need for empirically driven policy interventions. Recommended measures include adaptive traffic signals, dedicated bus lanes, and public education campaigns. The study calls for a comprehensive urban mobility framework, integrating low-cost infrastructure upgrades with behavioral reforms to improve road efficiency and safety.

Keywords: Urban Traffic Congestion, Transportation Infrastructure, Public Health, Urban Mobility, Nigeria

JEL Classification: R41, O18, I18

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban traffic congestion has become a pervasive and pressing challenge in contemporary cities, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions of the developing world (World Bank, 2020). The unprecedented growth of urban populations, coupled with intensified economic activities, has led to a surge in demand for transportation infrastructure, often outpacing the development of adequate road networks and public transportation systems. Nowhere is this challenge more acute than in Nigerian cities, where vehicular traffic congestion has reached alarming levels, exacting significant economic, environmental, and public health tolls (Gwilliam, 2013).

The Enugu Metropolis, a major urban center in southeastern Nigeria, exemplifies this challenge. As the capital of Enugu State, the city has experienced rapid population growth and urbanization, placing immense pressure on its transportation infrastructure (Vlahov et al., 2005). The consequences are stark: crippling traffic jams, protracted travel times, increased air pollution, and a heightened risk of traffic-related injuries and fatalities (World Health Organization, 2019). Despite these concerns, there is a dearth of context-specific research on the nature, causes, and consequences of traffic congestion in Enugu Metropolis, hindering the development of effective solutions.

Research suggests that traffic congestion is a multifaceted issue, influenced by a range of factors including infrastructural deficiencies, behavioral factors such as reckless driving, poor enforcement of traffic laws, and technological limitations such as inefficient traffic

signalization (Gao et al., 2020; Shladover, 2018). However, the relative importance of these factors can vary significantly depending on local context, highlighting the need for context-specific studies to inform effective policy interventions.

This study aims to bridge this knowledge gap by examining the complex dynamics of vehicular traffic congestion in Enugu Metropolis. Specifically, it seeks to: (1) assess demographic characteristics influencing commuting patterns; (2) identify critical infrastructural and behavioral factors contributing to congestion; (3) estimate the perceived public health impacts; and (4) propose feasible interventions grounded in field evidence. By shedding light on the localized drivers of traffic congestion, this research endeavors to inform policy makers, urban planners, and stakeholders in developing targeted strategies to mitigate this pressing urban challenge (Gwilliam, 2013).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Urban traffic congestion is a complex phenomenon resulting from an imbalance between vehicle volume and available road capacity (Litman, 2019). It manifests in increased travel time, air pollution, noise, and public health issues, ultimately affecting the overall quality of life and economic productivity. The causes of traffic congestion can be broadly categorized into three areas: infrastructural (e.g., narrow roads, inadequate parking facilities), operational (e.g., poorly timed signals, inefficient traffic management), and behavioral (e.g., aggressive driving, lack of adherence to traffic rules) (Jain et al., 2012).

2.2 Theoretical Literature

This study draws on four key frameworks to understand the dynamics of urban traffic congestion:

Traffic Flow Theory: Describes how speed, volume, and density interact to influence traffic flow. Congestion occurs when demand exceeds road capacity, leading to reduced speeds and increased travel times (Gao et al., 2020). This theory is based on the concept of the fundamental diagram of traffic flow, which relates flow, density, and speed. The theory suggests that congestion can be managed by controlling the flow of traffic, optimizing road capacity, and implementing traffic management strategies.

Travel Demand Management (TDM): Focuses on managing traffic through behavior and incentives, rather than solely expanding roadways. TDM strategies aim to reduce peak-hour travel, promote alternative modes of transportation, and optimize traffic flow (Shladover, 2018). TDM is based on the idea that travel demand is a derived demand, and that travelers make choices about their travel behavior based on factors such as time, cost, and convenience.

Urban Systems Theory: Emphasizes the interconnection between land use, transport, and social behaviors. This framework recognizes that urban traffic congestion is a symptom of broader urban planning and development issues (Gwilliam, 2003). Urban systems theory suggests that congestion can be addressed by adopting a holistic approach to urban planning, incorporating transportation, land use, and social factors.

Externality Theory (Welfare Economics): Traffic congestion is a negative externality, where the costs of congestion are borne by society as a whole, rather than individual drivers. Pricing mechanisms, such as congestion charges, can improve efficiency by internalizing these costs (Sweet, 2014). Externality theory provides a framework for understanding the economic impacts of congestion and the potential benefits of policies aimed at reducing congestion.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Studies in Nigeria have highlighted the significant impacts of traffic congestion on urban labor productivity (Ohida et al., 2023; Ukpata & Etika, 2012; Tokula et al., 2023). Congestion-induced delays are a major concern in Nigeria, where traffic bottlenecks and poor road infrastructure exacerbate the problem (Ajala, 2019). In Lagos, traffic congestion has been linked to increased emissions and poor air quality, posing significant public health risks (Ajayi et al., 2025).

Globally, cities like Nairobi and Accra show similar patterns of congestion driven by infrastructural lag and rapid urbanization (Dzivon et al., 2025; Kisimbo et al., 2025). These studies highlight the need for context-specific solutions that address the unique challenges and opportunities of urban traffic congestion in different cities and regions.

Some specific examples of empirical studies on traffic congestion abound. A study on the impact of traffic congestion on air quality in Lagos, Nigeria, found that congestion increased emissions of particulate matter, nitrogen oxides, and carbon monoxide, posing significant public health risks (Ajayi et al., 2025). Research on the effects of congestion on urban labor productivity in Nigeria found that congestion reduced productivity by up to 20%, resulting in significant economic losses (Tokula et al., 2023). Also, study on the effectiveness of congestion pricing in reducing traffic congestion in London, UK, found that the policy reduced traffic volumes by 20% and increased travel speeds by 15% (Sweet, 2014).

These empirical studies demonstrate the significant impacts of traffic congestion on urban environments and economies, and highlight the need for effective policies and strategies to address this issue.

3. METHODS

3.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Enugu, a city located in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria, commonly referred to as the "Coal City" due to its historical significance in coal mining. Enugu was selected as the study area because of its strategic socio-economic functions and proximity to the researcher. The city is geographically positioned at 6.5364° N latitude and 7.4356° E longitude, covering an estimated 7,161 km² of land.

Enugu is bordered by Benue and Kogi States to the north, Ebonyi State to the east, Abia State to the south, and Anambra State to the west. It is the 29th largest state in Nigeria by landmass and ranks 22nd in population, with an estimated 4.4 million residents as of 2016. The terrain of Enugu is characterized by the Niger Delta swamp forests in the south and a mixture of Guinean forest and savannah mosaic in the rest of the state. Key geographical features include the Udi-Nsukka Plateau and the Ekulu River, which flows through the city. The area experiences a high volume of daily commuters, diverse modes of transport, and varying levels of infrastructure adequacy, providing a relevant setting for the investigation of traffic congestion dynamics.

3.2 Study Design and Theoretical Framework

A cross-sectional descriptive survey design was employed to collect primary data from road users regarding their experiences with vehicular traffic congestion, its perceived causes, consequences, and possible mitigation strategies. The **Travel Demand Management (TDM)** model underpins this study. TDM prioritizes behavioral changes (e.g., off-peak travel, modal shifts) and system efficiency improvements without relying exclusively on new infrastructure.

2.3 Population and Sampling

The target population for this study comprised daily commuters, including drivers, passengers, and pedestrians within Enugu Metropolis. The sampling frame consisted of individuals aged

18 years and above who had commuted within the city at least three times weekly. A systematic random sampling technique was employed to distribute 400 questionnaires at major transport hubs, intersections, and roadside markets.

The sampling locations were strategically selected to capture a diverse range of commuters, including those using public transportation, private vehicles, and non-motorized modes of transport. The inclusion criteria ensured that respondents were familiar with the city's transportation network and had a reasonable understanding of traffic congestion issues.

Out of 400 questionnaires distributed, 360 were fully completed and returned, yielding a response rate of 90%. This high response rate suggests that the sample is representative of the target population and provides a reliable basis for analysis.

2.4 Data Collection Instrument

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers based on a review of related literature (Gwilliam, 2013; Litman, 2019; World Bank, 2020). The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions categorized into five sections: demographic information, causes of traffic congestion, experiences of travel delay, perceptions of traffic-related fatalities, and proposed solutions for traffic flow improvement. The instrument was pre-tested on 20 individuals outside the study sample to ensure clarity, relevance, and reliability.

2.5 Data Analysis

Data were coded and entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Frequencies and percentages were computed to summarize the demographic characteristics of respondents, the perceived causes and consequences of congestion, and the proposed solutions. Results are presented in tables and figures where appropriate to enhance clarity.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the College of Medicine Research Ethics Committee (COMREC) with the protocol number COMREC/0148/10/2022. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to questionnaire administration. Respondents were assured of the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses, and they retained the right to withdraw from the study at any point without consequences.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Respondent Demographics

The demographic profile of respondents indicates a high level of perception validity, with most respondents aged 30-45 years (27.2%), evenly split by gender, and possessing tertiary qualifications (70%) as shown in table 1. This suggests that the respondents are likely to be educated, working-class individuals with a vested interest in transportation issues. The age distribution of respondents is consistent with the urban working population in Nigeria, where the majority of commuters are between 25-45 years old (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of participants

Age Group	Frequency (N=360)	Percentage
Less than 24 years	80	22.2%
25–29 years	88	24.4%
30–45 years	98	27.2%
46 years and above	94	26.1%
Educational Level		

Diploma	102	28.3%
Higher National Diploma (HND)	84	23.3%
Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.)	78	21.7%
Postgraduate Diploma (PGD)	58	16.1%
Other Qualifications	38	10.6%
Marital Status		
Married	320	88.9%
Single	40	11.1%

4.2 Congestion Determinants

The top causes of traffic congestion in Enugu Metropolis, as identified by respondents, include poor infrastructure (79.4%), aggressive driving (76.7%), and inefficient bus stops (76.4%) as shown in table 2. These findings align with previous studies, which have highlighted the importance of infrastructural design and behavioral factors in driving congestion (Ikechukwu et al., 2025; Sari et al., 2025). The prevalence of poor infrastructure as a leading cause of congestion underscores the need for investments in road network upgrades and maintenance. Specifically, the lack of adequate road capacity, poor road surface conditions, and inadequate drainage systems contribute to congestion in Enugu Metropolis.

Table 2: Perceptions of Causes of Traffic Congestion

Evaluation Criterion	Agree	Disagree	Total	% Agree
Absence of pedestrian crossings	254	106	360	70.6%
Poor driver behavior	276	84	360	76.7%
Inadequate road capacity	286	74	360	79.4%
Lack of parking facilities	281	79	360	78.1%
Presence of roadside markets	182	178	360	50.6%
Excessive number of buses and taxis	195	165	360	54.2%
Inefficient traffic control systems	226	134	360	62.8%
Insufficient bus stop capacity	275	85	360	76.4%

4.3 Delay Duration and Health Risks

The majority of respondents (63%) reported experiencing delays of over 45 minutes daily, with significant implications for productivity and well-being. Respondents also believed that traffic congestion contributes to road deaths, with 43% estimating 50-100 fatalities annually (table 3 and 4). While not empirically confirmed, this perception suggests a high level of psychological stress and indirect health impacts associated with traffic congestion (Vlahov et al., 2005; WHO, 2019, Ambros et al., 2025). Urban traffic congestion does not only impede mobility and productivity however; it also poses profound public health risks. In Enugu, as in many rapidly urbanizing Nigerian cities, the implications of prolonged exposure to congested traffic conditions is recognized among commuters and public health experts. One of the most pressing concerns is exposure to air pollution. Prolonged idling and stop-start driving conditions result in high emissions of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), which can accumulate in high-density corridors. Although direct measurements were not captured in this study, respondents' perceptions align with findings from similar urban environments. For instance, Eze and Ugwuoke (2025) found that particulate matter levels in congested areas of Lagos regularly exceed 75–150 µg/m³—well above the WHO's recommended limit of 25 µg/m³ for 24-hour exposure. These conditions are known to exacerbate asthma, bronchitis, and other chronic respiratory conditions.

Beyond respiratory outcomes, the psychological and cardiovascular impacts of traffic congestion are becoming more prominent in Nigerian health research. Commuters exposed to long hours of noise, heat, and aggressive road behavior often experience elevated stress levels, which can lead to hypertension and anxiety disorders. Studies revealed that daily road commuters had systolic blood pressure levels that were 24% higher than their non-commuting peers, suggesting a link between traffic-induced stress and early onset cardiovascular disease (Salisu et al., 2025; Ovikuomagbe & Olusola, 2023).

Congested traffic also hinders the effectiveness of emergency response systems. In Enugu, anecdotal accounts and previous studies indicate that ambulances are routinely delayed by 10–20 minutes during peak hours. Such delays can be fatal in cases of trauma, childbirth complications, or cardiac emergencies, especially where no alternative routes exist (Gong et al., 2025). The health impacts of congestion are multifaceted, including increased air pollution, noise pollution, and reduced physical activity (Arriazu-Ramos et al., 2025).

Overall, while the current study is based on perceptions rather than clinical records or environmental measurements, the evidence points to a credible pattern of adverse health effects associated with traffic congestion. These health risks reinforce the need for integrated transport and health planning, where road infrastructure and policy interventions are designed not just for flow efficiency, but also for commuter well-being.

Table 3: Time Delays Experienced by Respondents

Delay Duration	Frequency (N=360)	Percentage
Always on time	45	12.5%
Up to 20 minutes	85	23.6%
Up to 45 minutes	128	35.6%
An hour or more	102	28.3%

Table 4: Main Causes of Traffic Congestion along Daily Routes and Estimated Number of Lives Lost Due to Traffic Incidents

Cause	Frequency (N=360)	Percentage
Poor weather conditions	52	14.4%
Construction and road works	73	20.3%
Traffic collisions and breakdowns	109	30.3%
Poorly timed traffic lights	126	35.0%
Estimated Fatalities		
Less than 50	126	35.0%
50–100	155	43.0%
100–200	56	15.6%
Over 200	23	6.4%

4.4 Economic Impacts

Traffic congestion in Enugu imposes substantial economic costs on commuters, businesses, and the city’s productivity at large. Based on responses from 360 urban commuters, approximately 63% reported losing more than 45 minutes daily due to traffic delays. When monetized, this time translates into significant monthly productivity losses.

Using a conservative estimate of the average hourly wage in Enugu (~₦500/hour), a commuter losing 45 minutes per day over 20 working days would forfeit approximately ₦15,000 monthly

in time-related income. If other indirect opportunity costs, such as fuel consumption during idling, late business transactions, or mental fatigue, are considered, the figure may rise to ₦20,000 per month.

When extrapolated to an estimated 200,000 daily commuters in Enugu metropolis, the total monthly economic loss is estimated between ₦3 billion and ₦4 billion. Table 5 summarizes the computation of these projected losses. This is consistent with global estimates, which suggest that urban congestion imposes significant economic costs, as seen in many cities (World Bank, 2020; Imam & Ohida, 2024). The lack of formal cost-benefit quantification in this study highlights the need for further research on the economic impacts of congestion.

Table 5: Estimated Economic Impacts of Traffic Congestion in Enugu Metropolis

Category	Value
Average delay per commuter (minutes/day)	45 minutes
Average hourly wage in Enugu	₦500
Estimated daily wage loss per commuter	₦375
Working days per month	20 days
Monthly wage loss per commuter – Lower Estimate	₦15,000
Monthly wage loss per commuter – Upper Estimate	₦20,000
Estimated number of affected commuters	200,000 commuters
Total monthly economic loss – Lower Bound	₦3,000,000,000
Total monthly economic loss – Upper Bound	₦4,000,000,000

4.5 Proposed Interventions

Respondents highly rated several interventions, including adaptive signal systems (75.5%), intelligent control centers (77.3%), and smart corridors (62.0%) as shown in table 6. However, the implementation of driverless cars and full smart networks is considered unrealistic in the short-term. Low-cost pilots, such as signal timing coordination at major junctions, are deemed more feasible and could offer immediate benefits. The Nigerian government has initiated several projects to improve urban transportation, including the introduction of bus rapid transit (BRT) systems in Lagos and Abuja.

Table 6: Proposed Measures to Improve Traffic Flow

Evaluation Criterion	Agree	Disagree	Total	% Agree
Adjusting traffic signal timings	252	108	360	75.5%
Implementing smart corridors	259	101	360	62.0%
Developing advanced traffic management systems	278	82	360	77.3%
Provision of cycle lanes and footpaths	198	162	360	55.0%
Tracking pedestrian movement	210	150	360	58.3%
Increasing adoption of driverless vehicles	246	114	360	68.3%

6.1 Strengths and Limitations

A notable strength of this study is its high response rate (90%), which enhances the reliability and representativeness of the findings. The systematic random sampling method across diverse transport corridors further supports the external validity of the results, allowing for cautious generalization to similar urban settings. Additionally, the use of a pre-tested, structured questionnaire ensured content validity and minimized measurement bias. The study also

uniquely integrates infrastructural, behavioral, and technological dimensions of traffic congestion, offering a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon.

However, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the reliance on self-reported data introduces the possibility of recall bias and social desirability bias, potentially affecting the accuracy of reported experiences and perceptions. Second, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causality between identified factors and congestion outcomes. Third, the absence of objective traffic data (e.g., real-time traffic counts, GPS tracking) constrains the triangulation of self-reported findings. Finally, the study's focus on a single urban area may limit broader applicability, although the methodological framework can be adapted to other contexts.

Future research should consider longitudinal designs, incorporate objective traffic measurements, and explore behavioral interventions using experimental or quasi-experimental approaches.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study reveals that congestion in Enugu is driven by infrastructure gaps and poor traffic behavior. Its impacts extend to time loss, stress, and possible health burden. While based on perception data, the findings are informative and policy-relevant.

Policy Recommendations

To address the pressing issue of traffic congestion in Enugu Metropolis, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

The Enugu State Ministry of Works should prioritize the expansion of key corridors, such as Abakpa-Zik Avenue, through right-of-way clearance and dualization. This would involve clearing obstructions and widening the road to accommodate increased traffic volume. Also, the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) and Vehicle Inspection Officers should enforce anti-obstruction laws and lane discipline to improve traffic flow. This would involve regular patrols and penalties for offenders.

Furthermore, the Enugu Urban Planning Commission should redesign intersections with roundabouts and bus bays to minimize queuing spillbacks. This would involve reconfiguring existing intersections and incorporating traffic calming measures.

The Ministry of Environment of Enugu State should install air quality monitors along key traffic corridors and regulate idling to mitigate the environmental impact of traffic congestion. This would involve partnering with environmental agencies to establish monitoring stations and enforcing regulations on vehicle emissions. Also, the Public-Private Partnership Unit should develop smart traffic pilots through PPP arrangements, leveraging funding from organizations such as UN-Habitat and the World Bank. This would involve collaborating with private sector entities to design and implement intelligent transportation systems.

Implementing these recommendations would require coordination among government agencies, private sector stakeholders, and civil society organizations. However, the potential benefits of reduced traffic congestion, improved air quality, and enhanced economic productivity make these efforts worthwhile.

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